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Big Data Analytics: Map Reduce Function using BIRCH Clustering Algorithm

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Abstract

It is well known that, in Big Data information is represented in unstructured form and NoSQL is used for query processing. The volume of data also too large and simple Query processing is not sufficient and irrelevant. From that large volume of data, extracting the knowledgeable information is a big challenge. To analyze that, various Big Data analytical techniques are available in the market, that uncovers hidden patterns, market trends, customer preferences and other useful information that can help the organization to take useful decisions within less amount of time. For such applications, Map reduces frame work has recently attracted, that was introduced by APACHE HADOOP. However, conventional Map-Reduce function uses K-Means Clustering algorithm, which will work efficiently on numerical data only with high time complexity. This paper gives an idea how BIRCH works efficiently on large databases concerning running time, space required, quality, the number of I/O operations applied. It shows linear scalability with respect to a number of objects.

Keywords: Big Data, Map Reduce, Data Set, BIRCH

1. Introduction

As technology evolved, information is digitized such as digital pictures, videos, records like humans, purchases etc will be digitized. However, as the volume of data increases exponential, the modern techniques are becoming out of date. To deal with bid data, it requires wide range of coding skills, statistics and domain knowledge.

The characteristics of big data can be specified with ten V's sum it up pretty well – Vision, Veracity, Velocity, Viscosity, Virality, Volume, Variety, Variability, Visualization and value.

Viscosity – Resistance flow in the volume of data will be measured.

Virality – How hastily data spread and shared to each unique node will be measured.

Vision – How much comprehensible knowledge an organization maintains will be measured.

Volume- The size of the data will be measured in the form Giga, Zetta, or Yotta bytes.

Velocity – How efficiently data is accessible will be measured.

Variety – different types of data from XML to videos to SMS may form unstructured data.

Variability – If the importance of data is constantly changing, it can have enormous impact on data homogenization.

Veracity – Accuracy of the data will be measured.

Visualization – The large volume of data will be visualized using charts and graphs effectively, for easy analysis.

Value – Retrieving value from data. It is the final output.

Fig 1: Big Data with various V's

2. Map Reducing Algorithm

It is a Distributed data processing algorithm that uses divide and conquers technique to process large volume of data in reliable, parallel and efficient way to cluster and classify. It divides input data into small convenient sub tasks to execute them in parallel.

Map Reduce uses the following two main step:

- Map Function- $(k1, v1) \rightarrow [(k2, v2)]$
- Reduce Function - $(k2, [v2]) \rightarrow [(k3, v3)]$

2.1 Map Function

It the first step in Map Reduce Algorithm. It divides the given input tasks into smaller sub-tasks. Then perform required computation on each sub-task in parallel.

This step performs the following two sub-steps:

- Splitting- The input data set from source will be divided into smaller Sub-Data Sets
- Mapping – On Sub-Data Sets perform required action or computation. The output of this Map Function is a set of key and value pairs as <Key, Value>

2.2 Reduce Function

Reduce function takes list of <Key, List<Value>> sorted pairs from Shuffle Function and perform reduce operation.

3. Word Count Algorithm in Map Reduce

The Pseudo-code for the word count algorithm in Map Reduce is shown below. The map emits an Intermediate key-value pair for each word in a document. The reducer sums up all counts for each word.

1. Class Mapping
2. Method map(file id, file txt)
3. For all items $I \in$ file do
4. Emit(item I, count 1)
5. Class shuffle
6. Method radix sort(File id)
7. For all items $I \in$ file do
8. Bucket sort(txt is not NULL)
9. Bucket sort (not EOF)
10. Method Bucket sort(File id)
11. list $Y[k+1]$
12. for $i = 0$ to k do $Y[i] =$ empty

13. while L nonempty
14. let X = first record in File
15. move X to Y[key(X)]
16. for i = 0 to k
17. concatenate Y[i] onto end of L
18. Class Reduce
19. Method Reducer(item I, count[c1,c2,...])
20. Sum:=0
21. For all count c ∈ count [c1,c2,...] do
22. Sum:=sum+c;
23. Emit(item I, count sum)

Example:

4. Balanced Iterative Reducing and Clustering using Hierarchies (BIRCH)

Grouping a set of objects on their similarity of attributes and their approximate in the vector space is referred to as Data Clustering. In map reduce function shuffle functions uses Data Clustering, the general algorithm used to cluster the data is K-Means clustering algorithm which only works on numerical data and will take more amount of time to cluster. This paper gives an idea how BIRCH works efficiently on large databases in terms of running time, space required, quality, number of I/O operations applied. It shows linear scalability with respect to a number of objects.

BIRCH is a scalable clustering method, designed for VLDB. A single scan of the dataset yields a good clustering and one or more additional passes can be used to improve the quality. It works based on the notation of CF (Clustering Feature) tree. CF vector of the cluster is defined as a triple:

CF = (N,LS, SS), where N is the number of data points in the cluster. LS is the Linear Sum of N points..i.e., $\sum_{i=1}^N X_i$. SS is the square sum of N points .i.e., $\sum_{i=1}^N X_i^2$

CF Additive Theorem : Assume CF1=(N1,LS1,SS1) and CF2=(N2,LS2,SS2) are the CF vectors of two disjoint clusters. Then the CF vector of the cluster that is formed by merging two disjoint clusters is:

4.1 CF Tree

CF Tree is a height balanced tree and build dynamically when new object is inserted. It has three parameters.

B = Branching Factor, maximum children in a non-leaf node

T = Threshold for diameter or radius of the cluster in a leaf

L = number of entries in a leaf

$CF = CF1 + CF2 = (N1 + N2, LS1 + LS2, SS1 + SS2)$.

4.2 CF tree structure

4.3 Basic Algorithm of BIRCH:

4.3.1 CF Tree Insertion

Start with the root, Find the CF entry in the root closest to the data point, move to that child and repeat the process until the closest leaf entry is found. At the leaf, If the point can be accommodated in the cluster, update the entry. If this addition violates the threshold T, split the entry, if this violates the limit imposed by L, split the leaf. If its parent node is full, split that and so on. Update the CF entries from the leaf to the root to accommodate this point.

Phase 1: Load data into memory.

Choose an initial value for threshold, start inserting the data points one by one into the tree as per the insertion algorithm. If, in the middle of the above step, the size of the CF tree exceeds the size of the available memory, increase the value of the threshold. Convert the partially built tree into a new tree. Repeat the above process until the entire dataset is scanned and a full tree is built.

Phase 2: Condense data.

A bridge between phase 1 and phase 3, It Builds a smaller CF tree by increasing the threshold.

Phase 3: Global clustering.

Apply global clustering algorithm to the sub-clusters given by leaf entries of the CF tree. It Improves clustering quality.

Phase 4: Cluster refining.

Scan the entire dataset to label the data points

Ex:

$$CF1 = (3, \langle 2+3+4, 5+2+3 \rangle, \langle 2^2+3^2+4^2, 5^2+2^2+3^2 \rangle)$$

$$= (3, \langle 9, 10 \rangle, \langle 29, 38 \rangle)$$

$$CF2 = (3, \langle 2+4+2, 3+5+4 \rangle, \langle 2^2+4^2+2^2, 3^2+5^2+4^2 \rangle)$$

$$= (3, \langle 8, 12 \rangle, \langle 24, 50 \rangle)$$

$$CF3 = CF1 + CF2 = (\langle 3+3 \rangle, \langle 9+8, 10+12 \rangle, \langle 29+24, 38+50 \rangle)$$

$$= (6, \langle 17, 22 \rangle, \langle 63, 88 \rangle)$$

5. Experimental Analysis

Performance Map-Reduce function when it uses K-Means clustering algorithm in shuffle function will take more amount of time, because the K-means clustering time complexity is $O(n)$. K-Means is Sensitive to noise and outliers. It Works well only with clusters of convex shapes Works and only on numerical data. So this paper proposes BIRCH clustering algorithm in shuffle function which less reduces the retrieval time because the time complexity of BIRCH algorithm is $O(\log n)$.

We evaluated the proposed algorithm on iris data sets from UCI machine learning repository [9]. We compared clustering results achieved by the k-means and BIRCH clustering algorithm. In each experiment, the accuracy and time were computed and taken the average accuracy and time of all experiments.

TABLE 1: PRINCIPLE COMPONENT ANALYSIS OF IRIS DATASET

COMPONENT	EIGEN VALUE	ACCUMALATION
1	4.224	92.46
2	0.242	97.76
3	0.078	99.48
4	0.023	100.0

Performance analysis of comparison of Map-Reduce function with K-Means and BIRCH algorithm is shown below

No. Of Clusters	Algorithm	Run	Accuracy	Time Taken(ms)
K=3	Map Reduce with K-Means	6	78.9	70.7
	Map Reduce with BIRCH	1	89.2	60

5. Conclusion

Recently Big Data Analytical techniques have encompassed every field in our life. These techniques are being used in the medical, banking, insurances, education, retail industry etc. Before working in the Big Data Analytical models, it is very important to have the knowledge of the existing essential algorithms.[8] Every algorithm has their significance, and we use them on the nature of the data, but on the basis of this research, we concluded that Map-Reduce function with k-means clustering algorithm is simplest algorithm as compared to other algorithms and its performance is better than Hierarchical Clustering algorithm and takes more time to retrieve the data. In this paper we proposed BIRCH algorithm in Map-Reduce function and analyzed through a sample data, which will reduce the retrieval time.

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